

INFORMATION SUPPORT IN THE PROCESS OF EMPLOYMENT OF UNIVERSITY GRADUATES

¹Sadullaeva Sh.A., ²Yakubov M.S., ³Parmankulov F.N.

¹Joint Belarusian-Uzbek Intersectoral Institute of Applied Technical Qualifications in Tashkent

²Department of Convergence of Digital Technologies/Computer Engineering Faculty, Tashkent
University of Information Technologies

³Joint Belarusian-Uzbek Intersectoral Institute of Applied Technical Qualifications in Tashkent

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Abstract. *The article reviews sources on the issue of graduate employment, systematizes the main approaches to studying the role of various social institutions in youth employment; analyzes employment statistics in the field of employment of graduates of the vocational education system and their integration into the labor market; develops methodological packages of tools, sample frames and a series of surveys; studies the attitudes of employers information needs of students and graduates regarding their employment opportunities were determined; recommendations were developed for optimizing employment policy in terms of the relationship between the educational services market and the labor market.*

Keywords: *employers, employment, educational services, labor market, personal need, vocational education, skilled labor.*

Within the framework of contemporary society's socio-economic shifts, recent graduates from postsecondary educational institutions frequently find themselves unemployed. A lot of young specialists with vocational education who are not tailored to the demands of the labor market are now appearing on the job market as a result of the liberalization of vocational education and employment systems, the industrial production crisis, and the expansion of the service sector. Because of their professional and sociodemographic traits, university graduates constitute a socially vulnerable population.

Therefore, the state is required to create the necessary social institutions at the regional levels and develop appropriate management mechanisms within the framework of a market economy, all the while relying on the values of human rights, the Republic of Uzbekistan's Constitution, and the principles of the social state.

Within the framework of the administrative-command system's transformation, which had previously formed enrollment indicators for universities and technical schools, enterprises planned their personnel composition with the renewal of the corps of specialists in mind. As a result, young specialists were restricted in their job choices even though they were guaranteed jobs. These days, student's future professional prospects are not solely and unequivocally determined by the university they attend. Consequently, there are many times as many persons who work outside of their expertise after graduating from a higher or secondary vocational education school, having finished their studies at the price of budget financing.

Some recent graduates are completely unemployed. The growing percentage of graduates who register with the job service after obtaining a vocational education is another concerning trend. Thus, the effectiveness of allocating budgetary resources for market regulation, professional training, and specialist retraining becomes a question [1-2].

Looking for solutions to coordinate the several agents involved in the employment and training of young specialists is relevant. Only democratic institutions, acting under the principles of social fairness and economic growth while considering the interests of the main players in this process—employers, workers, and educational institutions—can accomplish this.

The motivation behind a person's career choice and vocational education are qualitatively altered, their entire system of value preferences and life orientations are being reorganized, and the patterns of habitual entry of young people into the working phase of activity change. Stereotypes and ingrained opinions are unable to explain what is happening or offer advice on proper conduct. The younger generation is drawn to novel ideas, actions, and emerging systems. In this sense, youth objectives and attitudes, aspirational guides, and social norms and expectations are all modified.

This has led to an updating of the role of sociological research, which helps determine the priorities of social policy and vocational education management by offering unbiased information about the state of employment issues faced by graduates of vocational education institutions in the contemporary labor market as well as in the conditions of a particular region.

Youth employment strategies are evaluated based on how well they are optimized, how well they can adapt to changes in the external environment by updating their structure, how well they form appropriate professional potential, how well they activate individual capabilities, and how well youth groups implement appropriate behavior strategies. New technologies for work and employment, as well as new educational models, emerge in the context of society's digitization.

The issue of subjects in the educational process adapting to modern information systems is made real by modern technologies, which offer new ways to deliver training courses, but until far, only to specific populations. In order to provide job training and career assistance for unemployed citizens, the unemployed population, and laid-off workers, this calls for a social partnership ideology and increased contact with employers, government agencies, and other partners.

Organizing training centers for the employment system is a beneficial and important way to provide specialists from employment services and educational institutions with courses that are focused on topics related to employment and graduate adaptation. Simultaneously, more comprehensive prerequisites are needed for effective employment policies and strategies. These include systems for retraining and labor efficiency, the work of creating new jobs, and reducing the basics of non-market interactions and hidden unemployment.

The behavior of young groups in the job market and the effectiveness of youth employment strategies are now lacking in defined criteria. However, labor market policy is only a crucial component of employment policy, helping to address specific issues like resolving market economy imbalances, lessening the effects of unemployment, boosting youth mobility and competitiveness, and allowing for the precise criticism of ministries' and departments' actions due to the unavoidable and complete virtualization of scientific information, which can aid in overcoming departmental disunity at all levels.

It is shown in the framework of institutional interaction between educational institutions, employers (enterprises), and employment services to solve the issue of employment of graduates of vocational education institutions. It is feasible to draw attention to important theoretical and practical concerns brought on by the circumstances of cultural and economic change when the educational system is seen as a unique and essential social institution.

In the system of social division of labor, education is a social institution that consists of a variety of specialized institutions bound together by shared tasks and forming a distinct division of the social structure. It is also a system of unique social roles, actors, and norms that distribute and redistribute the symbolic resources of society while serving unique purposes in an individual's life. Three main categories of functions that education serves are typically economic, social, and cultural.

Under developed market relations, the shift from adult education to continual professional retraining is being made against the backdrop of a disheartening fall in educational institution efficiency and rising costs. The educational institution starts to grasp new market techniques in the context of extending democratic principles and decreasing state bureaucratic control. The primary actors functioning in the evolving educational field are groups of consumers and providers of educational services.

From an institutional perspective, the shift from formal to informal norms and rules governing economic behavior accounts for the widespread adoption of non-standard adaptation strategies. This shift permits a more adaptable response to changes while preserving a degree of marginality and half-heartedness [3-4].

In this scenario, social groupings of successful, adapted, and maladaptive people are separated, having distinct social and psychological features, if graduates in the labor market are evaluated in terms of adaptation. The degree of person's adaptation to societal changes is mostly influenced by their behavioral attitudes, particularly the passive, active, and neutral financial situation-assurance techniques they select.

Modifying the institutional framework of the labor market is one strategy for restructuring it in transition economies. In the labor market, where personal connections have historically been the most important channel for employment, the growth of formal organizations that offer employment assistance is crucial. Failure to do so will undoubtedly have negative effects on the labor market as a whole.

Whether to focus on other employment channels or contact the employment service when seeking for a job depends on a number of things. First and foremost, these are the characteristics of individual's resources in the labor market: sociodemographic (gender, age, education), economic (financial situation, employment status at the time of application), and features of the job search strategy. They also include subjective evaluations of individual's marketability and opinions regarding the efficacy of institutional market channels.

The results' analysis persuades that, throughout the preceding ten years, young people have undergone complicated processes that point to a reevaluation of the cultural values of earlier generations and a rupture in the continuity of the sociocultural experience's transmission. While many young people dread unemployment, they have hope for their chosen vocation in the future [5]. In general, assessments and opinions about the task that lies ahead tend to be pragmatic. The majority of young people think that while employment has a socially beneficial and creative value, we also need to remember to make money.

For the tenth person, any job will do as long as it pays well; for the fifth person, work will only be important if it allows them to pursue their personal goals and interests first. Young people want higher education, computer proficiency, foreign language proficiency, business acumen, the capacity to reason and behave responsibly in a market economy, and legal training in order to boost their self-confidence.

The majority of educational institutions function under the administrative system, whereas market relations have already fully taken over in the production sector. First and foremost, young people who obtain vocational education that is insufficient to meet the demands of the labor market are the captive of this disparity. This makes young people's already precarious position in the labor market even more discriminating [6-7].

Higher education graduates were the most competitive group in the 2010s registered labor market, with the highest percentage of employment, according to an analysis of the employment of unemployed graduates. The employment percentage for secondary vocational education graduates without jobs was almost 40%. We can deduce that "urban" and "female" unemployment predominates among graduates in the area based on the breakdown of unemployed graduates by place of residence as well as gender considerations.

The percentage of graduates among all unemployed people is currently declining, while the overall number of graduates applying to the employment service is rising; a rise in the proportion of graduates from secondary and higher vocational education institutions relative to all graduates; a fall in the proportion of graduates from primary vocational education institutions relative to all graduates; a rise in the proportion of women among graduates; and the highest number of unemployed graduates are referred for retraining to study in secondary vocational education institutions [8].

Financing for the training of specialists by interested enterprises, including the payment of scholarships by interested organizations to students who are preparing at a university to work in a given organization in a given profile, is one possible model for encouraging enterprises to hire graduates. A scholarship from extra-budgetary sources may prove to be a valuable instrument in addressing the organization's personnel shortages, developing human capital at the nexus of current specializations, and enabling personnel to specialize in a particular area of work. The issue of customized training for businesses might be resolved in this way.

Businesses that say they don't need to hire young experts differ in what they do, but the majority of them are service-oriented, doing everything from producing advertisements and cleaning buildings to offering medical services.[6] Trade organizations make up a relatively tiny portion of those who do not require young people, with industrial firms coming in second. The demand for university graduates is strongly correlated with the demands of the labor market, particular job categories, and the features of a particular economic sector.

The survey data indicates that there is a greater need for young specialists in small cities. The most interested parties are technical specialists. The chemical sector still has a need for managers, socioeconomic workers, medical professionals, and specialists. Naturally, this demand is structured in part by the economic characteristics of the area [9-10].

When a tripartite agreement between the company, the student, and the university is concluded, managers look for assurances of the specialist's return to the company. Executives who participated in the study expressed support for the introduction of tax incentives for businesses that fund the development of new experts and the establishment of trustee boards. The heads of universities received requests from the heads of enterprises expressing their desire to improve specialist training and to increase university-industry contacts (awareness of the needs of the enterprise, student practices at the enterprise, etc.).

Ensuring young people's social protection and adaptability during the market economy's transition is a crucial responsibility of the employment system as a whole and graduate

employment agency in particular. Three approaches are anticipated to be taken to address this issue: setting up career counseling and sociopsychological work with youth; setting up excellent vocational training; and creating more jobs, including temporary ones to guarantee youth and adolescent employment during their free time.[8]

Employment services and electronic recruitment companies are growing quickly in the nation. It should be noted that although these terms are sometimes used interchangeably, the official distinction between employment services and recruitment agencies is that the former's services are funded by employers, while the latter's are funded by candidates. Additionally, university recruitment agencies receive funding from a variety of sources, including the state budget. Many of these new partners in the electronic labor market are affiliated with colleges; occasionally, these agencies are run by students and recent graduates and are housed on university servers [11].

An examination of expert interviews revealed a problem that is crucial for today's workforce: the labor market intermediaries' social duty. Employment and recruitment experts concentrate on forming an organizational culture in the area, conducting market assessments, coordinating the release of new specialists, and responding to the always shifting labor demand. Experts say that evaluating labor market need is critical to developing in-demand professionals.

A cursory look reveals the potential of information technology and computer specialists, as well as trained sales managers and sales professionals. Hiring a graduate does not always guarantee quick profits. The decision to hire a graduate for an employer involves weighing the benefits and drawbacks of taking this action [12].

During the interview, several issues about student recruitment firms were clarified, including their technological setup, absence of feedback channels, and service payment issue. Respondents proposed special courses at colleges and even altering the entire educational process as a way to address the issue of hiring graduates. The interview also covered the issues surrounding interdepartmental communication in the workplace [13]. Joint ventures between an employer and a university are feasible and required from the perspectives of a non-state employment service and a university recruitment agency.

The task of interacting with employment services is controversial, mainly because of the mistrust that has been voiced regarding the state bureaucratic structure, which has been condemned for being overly opaque and ritualistic. At the moment, it is important to define precisely what student recruitment organizations do. Three key levels of activity appear promising: companies, university faculties and departments, and applicants and students.

While acknowledging the limitations of their own resources for significant work with departments and faculties to rectify or modify curricula that do not match the demands of the contemporary labor market and the need for experts, the directors of student recruiting agencies use a similar approach. There are a lot of conversations about the issue of young people's career guidance and selecting the right specialty. The issue of staffing the agency itself is linked to the operations of student recruitment agencies.

There are currently two clear models for organizing student recruitment agencies: the first model assumes a staff of university employees who are also members of the trade union; while students can volunteer, they are typically not very involved in work.

The second model involves a staff of students who are in their final years of study. Recruitment agency specialists identify the issue of "natural staff turnover" in the first case; they

must annually train new hires to replace those who have graduated from an educational institution. However, this issue does not appear to affect everyone, and this is perceived as a unique characteristic of student recruitment agencies, which must constantly be in flux.

The second model typically describes "stagnant" student recruiting organizations that are unable to actively promote the employability and competitiveness of their university's student body for both objective and subjective reasons [13]. Many universities are currently working on projects that will be made available for employment online.

On an electronic recruitment agency's website, graduates can have access to special sections with job openings, electronic conferences where graduates can ask any questions about working or attending a university, and an employment questionnaire where employers can view resumes. In this case, the public employment agency can and ought to function as both a rival and substitute for private recruiting firms and as a collaborator in the socioeconomic advancement of the locality, the nation, and even the world.

Conclusion: Low-efficiency hiring, employment, and education institutions' interactions that rely on employing graduates of higher education institutions. Several classifications of graduates and some social groups are not able to survive market competition.

One of the most urgent issues right now is finding a job worries of a few pupils.

Many young individuals experience difficulty integrating into the market due to inconsistent techniques for picking a life trajectory path and reasons for admittance to educational institutions work.

The failure of recent graduates to completely embrace who they are in market circumstances lead to dissatisfaction with their selected profession, or switching careers, which causes the state's value to decline costs associated with tertiary education, decline in intellectual potential, the rise of social unrest in the next years.

Inconsistency and orientations outside of professional and value orientations are among the causes of the mismatch between young people's life objectives and professional plans heightened communication across participants in the young market.

Work by itself won't provide a favorable outcome, this procedure can be guaranteed by the influence on labor market representatives when, direct or indirect control is carried out with directive planning behavior of market participants by producing fresh data, impacting the process of making decisions.

The employment service can act as an impartial outside expert whose knowledge, if any, is trustworthy and influences labor market actors' decisions because lowers their expenses, but in doing so, it also lowers their costs, raising effectiveness of market regulation of contemporary employment firms.

It's essential to simulate information exchange between participants in the labor market and evaluate the amount and caliber of information, which they require.

In relation to the production sector's structural changes, the demand for professionals has decreased, there aren't any present or long-term projections of the socioeconomic development of the areas, inadequate contact with businesses regarding the education of experts for certain jobs resulted in modifications to system's guidelines.

Individuals with secondary and postsecondary vocational education receiving training. Therefore, when choosing areas of engagement Educational establishments mostly concentrate on

Professional education that is necessary for each individual, not for actual needs of local labor markets.

University career advising systems are struggling to develop because students aren't given enough opportunities or motivated to engage with employers. There is a documented lack of administrative and financial resources, but there is still no information resource that is involved that drives labor market participants to utilize in the open and active resources in the necessary path.

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